

COMPRESSION PROPERTIES OF METAL BEETLE ELYTRON PLATES AND EXPLORATION OF THE ELEMENTARY UNIT IN THE CORE STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the mechanical properties of metal beetle elytron plates (BEPs, a type of bionic sandwich structure) and the elementary unit of the trabecular-honeycomb core structure by compression experiments. The following conclusions are drawn: 1) after reaching the compressive strength, the stress-strain curve of the BEP contains a yield plateau that advantageously exploits the material properties of metal and its plastic deformation capacity; 2) the elementary unit of the core structure in BEPs is proposed explicitly based on the trabecular characteristic; and 3) this elementary unit remains relatively unchanged on the constraint condition of the trabecular structure and has high independence and stability when placed under out-of-plane compression. Thus, the yield plateau and variation tendency of the compressive strength after buckling of this elementary unit are highly consistent with the compressive properties of the entire structure, which provides the basis for further research on the equivalent parameters and equivalent model of the BEP and its trabecular-honeycomb core structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

The collisions and impacts that occur in various types of disasters pose a tremendous threat to the safety of human lives and property. Therefore, structures and materials that offer high-deformation energy absorption capabilities are in high demand due to their crashworthiness and impact resistance [1-3]. A type of lightweight, high-strength structure used for this purpose is the honeycomb plate [4-6], which has been used in various fields [7-9]. In nature, various species of beetles have survived since the age of dinosaurs. Through their long evolution process, beetle elytra have developed a remarkable biological structure that exhibits several unique biological functions. For example, the structural color on the surfaces of beetle elytra is a typical example of the combination of a subtle fine structure and camouflage [10-12]. In addition, the inner three-dimensional structure of elytra, which imparts various biological functions, such as protection of the main body of the insect and facilitation of flight, is considered an advanced evolutionary biological structure that is both lightweight and high strength and exhibits excellent impact dissipation performance [13-15]. Our group has performed bionic studies of beetle elytra and found that their structure is composed of a fully integrated trabecular-honeycomb plate [16]. A beetle elytron (Fig. 1a) consists of both upper and lower skins as well as honeycomb walls and thousands of trabeculae (Fig. 1b, c), constituting a typical sandwich structure. Each trabecula has an external layer of chitin fibers and an internal core filled with protein (Fig. 1d). Experiments on the beetle elytron plate (BEP, a type of bionic sandwich structure), inspired by *A. dichotoma* elytra and conducted by JX Chen (Fig. 1a), based on the characteristics of a trabecular-honeycomb structure (Fig. 1b, c) have directly verified the favorable properties of this structure [17,18].

Fig. 1 Beetle and microstructure. (a) Adult *A. dichotoma* beetle [16]. (b) Location distribution of trabeculae in the fresh elytron of *A. dichotoma* [19]. The region is between the two right-angled arrows. (c) Trabecular shape [15]. (d) Simple model of a trabecula [15]. Trabeculae are indicated by broad arrows, and honeycomb walls are indicated by a star.

The natural biological structure of beetle elytra consists primarily of fibers. Synthetic sandwich plates currently used as engineering materials in various fields can consist of aluminum alloys, composite materials, plastics, papers and various other materials; whereas, metal is one of the most widely used class of material in sandwich structures and is expected to enable the broad applications. Thus, the mechanical properties of BEP structures made of metal will be investigated in this paper. Furthermore, similar to the honeycomb structure [20-22], because the anisotropy of the trabecular-honeycomb structure increases the complexity of mechanical analysis, correlational study of the elemental unit and equivalent parameters will provide an important foundation for the calculation and design of the BEP structure. Thus, primarily, it is necessary to explore and study the elemental unit of BEPs. Because sandwich theory can only make the core structure equal to the orthotropic homogeneous continuous structure and considers that the sandwich plate is composed of upper and lower isotropic skins and a middle anisotropic core structure [23]. In this paper, the compression performances of metal BEP are investigated through a comparison with the honeycomb plate, and the elementary unit of a BEP is proposed based on its trabecular structure, which will provide a basis for further research on the equivalent parameters and equivalent model of the BEP and its trabecular-honeycomb core structure.

2 PREPARATION AND EXPERIMENT METHOD

2.1 DESIGN AND PREPARATION OF SAMPLES

According to previous findings regarding the trabecular distribution in beetle elytra [19], the experimental models of the sandwich plates are shown in Fig. 2 for a convenient bionic design and mechanical analysis. Here, L is the honeycomb unit dimension (or the distance between the central points in adjacent trabeculae, which is 10 mm); R is the outer radius of the trabecula (2.5 mm); T is the core wall thickness (0.4 mm); H is the total height of the sandwich plates (12 mm), and the upper and lower skins are each 1 mm thick. For a convenient comparison, the BEP and honeycomb plate can be considered a composite structure consisting of honeycomb walls and column structures located at the intersections of these walls: the trabeculae (cylindrical shell) exist in the BEPs, and triangular columns are used in the honeycomb plates. Thus, the structures shown in Fig. 2b, c (dotted box) were chosen as the elementary unit (Fig. 2b1, c1) of core structure of a BEP and honeycomb plate, respectively. The core structures of these two sandwich plates and their corresponding elementary units were produced by 3D printing technology (M290, Eos GmbH, Germany). Furthermore, the core structures were attached to the upper and lower skins by glue (Ergo 5910-1, Switzerland) to form the sandwich plates.

Fig. 2 Dimensions and structures of the sandwich plates. (a) Overall dimensions; (b, b1) trabeclar-honeycomb core structure of a BEP and its elementary unit; (c, c1) core structure of a honeycomb plate and its elementary unit. In the figure, the thickness of the trabeclar structure is equal to that of the honeycomb walls.

2.2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The material properties of the metal used in 3D printing was obtained by tensile experiments, as shown in Fig. 3a. Tensile and compression experiments on the sandwich plates and corresponding elementary units were conducted using a T5305 electronic testing machine manufactured by MTS (Fig. 3b). The test models (using three samples for each type of plate) were subjected to displacement loading at a rate of 1 mm/min. It is well known that the compressive properties of a sandwich plate are determined by its core layer. Because the cross-sectional areas of the core structure of those two sandwich plates are different (the cross-sectional area of the core structure of the BEP is 50% greater than that of the honeycomb plate), the stress-strain curve of the core structure is employed to compare the difference of their compressive properties (The stress is calculated by dividing the force by the cross-sectional area of the core structure, whereas the strain is calculated by dividing the vertical deformation by the height of the core structure). Because the deformation occurs primarily in the core structure under this experimental condition, the energy absorption of unit volume of core structure (formula 1, hereafter referred to as the energy absorption capacity, in which the volume of the core structure V_c is used because the material density of BEPs and honeycomb plates is the same) is used as the index to evaluate the energy absorption capacity obtained in the compression experiment:

$$E_c = \frac{\int_0^D F d\delta}{V_c} \quad (1)$$

where E_c is the energy absorption of unit volume of core structure; $F = \sigma A$ is the vertical load on the core structure, σ is the stress in the core structure, A is the cross-sectional area of the core structure; $\delta = \varepsilon h$ is the vertical deformation of the core structure, ε is the vertical strain in the core structure, h is the height of the core structure; $D = \varepsilon_{max} h$ is the maximum deformation of the core structure, ε_{max} is the maximum strain in the core structure; and V_c is the volume of the core structure.

Fig. 3 Stress-strain curve and experimental methods. (a) Tensile behavior of the metal material. (b) Compression experiment. In (b), the different locations of the sample and the upper and lower experimental platforms are labeled because these two platforms are specular.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Compression properties of the metal BEP

Fig. 4 shows the experiment results of the two types of sandwich plates. In the metal BEP, S-type compressive deformation (Fig. 4a: BEP, arrow) predominantly occurs in the honeycomb walls and the trabeculae of the core structure exhibit a compression under a vertical load (Fig. 4a: BEP, star), whereas the honeycomb plate undergoes C-type half-wave deformation (Fig. 4a: HP, arrow), and the intersections of the honeycomb walls exhibit a twist (Fig. 4a: HP, star). These phenomena of metal BEPs are consistent with the BEPs composed of engineering resin [18], which indicates that the deformation forms of the BEP have a high degree of stability for different materials. However, the stress-strain curves of the metal sandwich plates differ from those of the engineering resin material due to the difference in the material properties between metal and resin. For comparison, Fig. 4a also provides the mechanical curve of the metal material and divides it into three sections (I-III) in accordance with the rise, yield plateau and fall. The honeycomb plate exhibits only the rise (I) and fall (II) stages, i.e., the stress immediately declines after reaching the highest point, 1. Thus, it cannot sufficiently utilize the material properties, particularly the plastic deformation capacity after metal yielding. In contrast, the compressive curve of the BEP is highly consistent with the three stages of a metal material, particularly the yield plateau. Although the stress-strain curve of the BEP reaches the highest point (Fig. 4a, point 1) and the descent point (Fig. 4a, point 2) in advance relative to the material itself, the difference in the width of the yield plateau between them (Fig. 4a, the distance between points 1 and 2 of metal and BEP) is approximately only 5%. This result indicates that the BEP can better exploit the plastic deformation capacity of metal materials relative to the honeycomb plate.

Fig. 4 Deformation and experimental results of the BEPs and honeycomb plates and tensile behavior of the base material. (a) Stress-strain curve of the core structure and its deformation form. (b) Compressive strength and energy absorption capacity. “HP” refers to the honeycomb plate.

Further analysis shows that the compressive strength of the honeycomb plate is 733 MPa (the compressive strength refers to the highest stress of each stress-strain curve, and the stress is calculated by dividing the force by the cross-sectional area of the core structure), less than half of the material strength, and the corresponding strain is 0.037. However, in BEPs, the compressive strength is 1,445 MPa, which is 97% greater than that of the honeycomb plate. What’s more, because the BEP has the same yield plateau II, which is consistent with the material properties, its core structure can be continuously deformed under a nearly invariable vertical load. The corresponding maximum strain is 0.1, which is 2.7 times that of the honeycomb plate. In other words, for out-of-plane compression, the stress of core structure in honeycomb plate can only reach to 733MPa and immediately declines; whereas the stress in BEP core structure can reach up to 1,445 MPa and last for a time. Thus, even if the vertical load reaches its compressive strength in a special case, the BEP can still maintain a constant bearing capacity during its plastic deformation, which results in noticeable signs of

deformation to remind the user to replace the sandwich plate or to allow for more escape time. Thus, this configuration can better ensure the safety of people's lives and property. Because of the compressive strength and deformation characteristics of the BEP structure, the energy absorption capacity during the compressive experiment is also significantly (4.86 times) higher than that of the honeycomb plate. That is, due to the trabeculae in the core structure, the compression performances of the BEP configuration is better than that of the honeycomb plate.

3.2 Compression properties of the elementary unit in the trabecular-honeycomb core structure

As noted above, it is necessary to explore and study the elemental unit of BEPs to provide an important foundation for the calculation and design of the BEP structure. Therefore, the main task of this mapper is to select an appropriate elementary unit in trabecular-honeycomb core structure. This paper, based on the trabecular characteristics of the BEP structure, explicitly proposes the elementary unit of its core structure, as shown in Fig. 5a (the rectangular dotted box). This elementary unit has the following characteristics: 1) the wall thickness of the elementary unit is the same as its original core structure; 2) in each rectangular dotted box, there are a trabecula and three honeycomb walls (Fig. 5a, the red unit), and the neighboring unit can be considered to use only the honeycomb walls to connect with each other; thus, every trabecula is relatively independent; and 3) this elementary unit structure consists of a trabecula (or cylindrical shell) reinforced by honeycomb walls, and the reinforcement is on the outside of the cylindrical shell, as shown in Fig. 2b1.

The sandwich theory considers that the sandwich plate consists of upper and lower isotropic skins and a middle anisotropic core structure. When the equivalent orthogonal anisotropic layer of sandwich structure is placed under a load in the in-plane (x and y directions) and out-of-plane, the mechanical properties and equivalent parameters will depend on the elementary unit [21]. Thus, an elementary unit of the trabecular-honeycomb core structure in a BEP is proposed, furthermore, this article primarily explores the feasibility of this elementary unit by studying the compressive performance of elastic deformation and post-buckling of sandwich plates and the corresponding elementary units under vertical loads (out-of-plane compression). Other loading conditions will be considered in subsequent studies. However, because of the reciprocal constraint between elementary units, the mechanical properties of the sandwich core structures differ from those of their elementary units. In particular, because of the thin-walled characteristic of the sandwich structures, the buckling behavior of the equivalent models is generally inconsistent with that of their original structures. Thus, to explore the independence and stability of the compression properties of the elementary unit in the BEP, the area in the rectangular dotted box in Fig. 5a is used to consider the elementary unit of a honeycomb plate for comparison, as shown in Fig. 2c1.

Fig. 5 (a) Elementary unit of the trabecular-honeycomb core structure in a BEP. (b) Compressive stress-strain curves of core structures of the two types of sandwich plates and their elementary units.

For comparative purposes, Fig. 5b presents the experimental results of the two types of sandwich plates (part of Fig. 4a) and the elementary units of their core structures. The stress-strain curve of the BEP elementary unit is basically consistent with the origin sandwich plate both in the elastic range and during post-buckling for out-of-plane compression. In particular, the difference in the compressive strength between the BEP and its elementary units is approximately 7%, and the corresponding strains are both approximately 0.06. In contrast, in the honeycomb plate, the elementary unit has a large gap in the post-buckling strength and variation tendency relative to the entire plate, except in the initial elastic range. The differences in the compressive strength and the corresponding strains are approximately 17.6% and 22%, respectively. After reaching the compressive strength, the stress in the curve of honeycomb plates declines with a nearly invariable slope, as shown in Fig. 5b (HP). However, its elementary unit appears as a concave curve, as shown in Fig. 5b (HP; unit). Until the strain is nearly 0.12, the downtrend of the honeycomb plate is close to that of its elementary unit. This phenomenon illustrates that the elastic deformation and plastic behavior between the BEP and its elementary unit are similar and stable, and this elementary unit could closely reflect the real mechanical properties of the entire structure when it undergoes out-of-plane compression. In fact, the upper and lower skins, which are joined to the core structure by glue, still constrain and reinforce the trabecular-honeycomb structure with a little influence during the compressive experiment. Thus, if the vertical load is imposed on only the trabecular-honeycomb core structure, the stress-strain curve of which would be more consistent with that of the elementary unit.

The reason is that the honeycomb plate relies on the honeycomb wall structure (thin plate) to bear the vertical load. However, the constraint and mechanical conditions of the honeycomb walls are always simplified or changed to a certain extent regardless of how the elementary unit is selected, which leads to a discrepancy between the stress-strain curves of the honeycomb core and its elementary unit. Similar to the case of the elementary unit of a honeycomb plate as described in this paper, when the elementary unit of honeycomb structure is under compression, the constraint from neighboring unit is simplified and ignored, which leads to the obvious difference between honeycomb plate and its elementary unit. However, as shown in Fig. 4a, the deformation form of core structure is from C-type (honeycomb plate) to S-type (BEP) when the trabecular structure is designed in the core structure; furthermore, the deformation form of intersections of the honeycomb walls is from twist (honeycomb plate) to compression (BEP). Besides, according to the compression properties mentioned in 3.1 chapter, it is known that the trabeculae represent a key mechanical structure in BEPs sandwich structure. However, this elementary unit centers on the trabecula and possesses three honeycomb walls as its reinforced structure, and the neighboring unit can be considered to use only the honeycomb walls to connect with each other; thus, the trabecula itself is relatively independent. In other words, when this structure is selected as the elementary unit of BEPs, the constraint condition of the key trabeculae remains relatively unchanged. Thus, relative to the elementary unit of the honeycomb plate, this cylindrical-shell-reinforced structure is more stable when placed under out-of-plane compression. In addition, the yield plateau achieved after reaching the compressive strength and the strength variation tendency post-buckling are basically consistent with the mechanical properties of the entire structure.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigates the mechanical properties of metal BEPs and corresponding elementary unit of the trabecular-honeycomb core structure by compression experiments. The following conclusions can be drawn:

(1) The stress-strain curve of the honeycomb plate contains only the rise and fall stages. In contrast, the compressive curve of BEPs is highly consistent with the three stages of a metal material, i.e., it exhibits a yield plateau. This sandwich structure can better employ the mechanical properties of the metal material and exhibits excellent plastic deformation capacity (2.78 times that of the honeycomb plate). Moreover, the BEP can still maintain a constant bearing capacity during its plastic deformation, which results in noticeable signs of deformation to remind the user to replace the sandwich plate or to allow for additional escape time.

(2) The elementary unit of the core structure in BEPs is proposed explicitly based on the trabecular characteristic and exhibits the following characteristics: 1) the wall thickness of the

elementary unit is the same as its original core structure. 2) One unit contains a trabecula and three honeycomb walls, and the neighboring unit can be considered to use only the honeycomb walls to connect with each other; thus, every trabecula is relatively independent. 3) This elementary unit structure is a trabecula (or cylindrical shell) reinforced by honeycomb walls, and the reinforcement is on the outside of the cylindrical shell.

(3) The elementary unit of a BEP centers on the trabeculae and reserves three honeycomb walls as its reinforced structure; in addition, the neighboring unit can be considered to use only the honeycomb walls to connect with each other. Therefore, the constraint condition of the key trabecular structure remains relatively unchanged. Thus, the yield plateau and variation tendency of the compressive strength after buckling of this elementary unit are highly consistent with the compressive properties of the entire structure, which will provide a further basis for study of the equivalent parameters and equivalent model of the BEP and its trabecular-honeycomb core structure.

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